

Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) and Soybean (*Glycine max L.*) Crop: A Review

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ABSTRACT

The present review paper offers a comprehensive examination of the potential advantages associated with the utilization of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria in the context of soybean (*Glycine max L.*) crop production. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the importance of Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) in the production of soybean crops. The investigation of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria and their capacity to augment the nutrition of plants and provide protection against diseases has been extensively explored in the literature.

This research aims to assess the efficacy of Plant Growth-Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) in enhancing soybean crop yield and elucidate its significance for promoting plant growth and defense mechanisms. In addition, an examination is conducted on the various processes by which Plant Growth-Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) interacts with soybean plants and contributes to their growth and development. In addition, we analyze the challenges and potential advantages associated with the use of PGPR-based approaches within soybean production systems. Research findings suggest that the application of PGPR has been demonstrated to significantly boost soybean germination rates and promote the uptake of nutrients by the plant.

Hence, additional investigation and field experiments are required in order to comprehensively comprehend the potential of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) in soybean cultivation and to design appropriate strategies for integrating them effectively into agricultural techniques.

Keywords: Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR), *Glycine max L.*

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Introduction

The production of soybean is of significant importance in the agricultural industry. The production of

soybeans holds great significance in the agricultural industry. Soybeans are a major crop that is widely grown for its versatile uses, such as food production, animal feed,

and biofuel. Moreover, soybeans are an essential source of protein and oil, making them a valuable commodity in the global market. (Sintaha, M. et al., 2022, Anang, T, B., Amesimeku, J. and Fearon, D, J., 2021) PGPR are beneficial bacteria that reside in the rhizosphere, the area surrounding plant roots. These bacteria have been found to enhance plant growth and development by improving nutrient uptake, stimulating root growth, suppressing pathogenic organisms, and enhancing tolerance to abiotic stress. (Ahmed, A. and Hasnain, S., 2014, Raimondi, G. et al., 2021, Costa-Gutierrez, B, S. et al., 2021)

The rhizosphere, the region surrounding plant roots, is inhabited by a group of beneficial bacteria known as Plant Growth-Promoting Rhizobacteria. Extensive research has elucidated their positive effects on various crops in terms of mitigating abiotic stresses and boosting productivity. Among economically significant crops such as rice, soybean, lettuce, tomato, maize, and wheat; PGPRs have demonstrated remarkable outcomes in improving yield under challenging conditions. (Işçi, B., Kacar, E. and Altindişli, A., 2019, Qessaoui, R. et al., 2019, Wang, L. et al., 2022, Işçi, B., Kacar, E. and Altindişli, A., 2019, Karagöz, P, F. and Dursun, A., 2019, Mathew, T, B. et al., 2020)

One key mechanism through which these PGPRs contribute to enhanced plant performance is via the production of essential plant growth regulators like gibberellic acid and indole acetic acid. Cattelan et al found that certain putative PGPR strains displayed significant benefits for shoot or root growth in soybeans while actively synthesizing IAA (indole acetic acid) or ACC deaminase. However, it was observed that these specific strains did not influence nodulation positively. Interestingly enough though non-IAA-producing bacteria were also capable of eliciting synergistic effects when co-inoculated with rhizobia during symbiosis formation between legume plants and rhizobia. (Xing, P. et al., 2022, Kang, S. et al., 2019, Numan, M., Serba, D, D. and Ligaba-Osena, A., 2021)

The influence exerted by soybean rhizosphere-derived PGPR hormones plays an instrumental role similar to other crop systems concerning host development. The production of PGPR for soybean crops holds immense potential in improving crop yield and sustainability. (França, S, d, R, A. et al., 2020, Sengupta, A. and Gunri, K, S., 2015)

Further research has shown that the interaction between soybean and PGPR is not solely dependent on the production of indole acetic acid, but rather influenced by multiple factors. These factors include plant genotype, PGPR strain, inoculation dose, environmental conditions, and the structure of the soil microbial community. (Stajković-Srbinović, O. et al., 2021, Xing, P. et al., 2022). In addition to hormone production, PGPR bacteria have been found to excrete various physiologically active compounds, such as phytohormones and metabolites, which contribute to the stimulation of plant growth. This stimulation occurs by alleviating the negative effects of abiotic stresses and increasing resilience to changing climatic conditions. (Ahmed, A. and Hasnain, S., 2014, Işçi, B., Kacar, E. and Altindişli, A., 2019, Raimondi, G. et al., 2021, Biswas, S., Nath, A. and Pal, K, R., 2021).

This review aims to discuss the current state of PGPR production for soybean crops, examining the benefits and challenges associated with its use.

PGPR Mechanisms in Soybean Crop

The use of PGPR for soybean crops has demonstrated numerous benefits in improving crop yield and sustainability. These include (Fig.1)

- **Enhanced plant growth:** PGPR bacteria produce essential plant growth regulators like gibberellic acid and indole acetic acid, which promote shoot and root growth in soybean plants (Xing, P. et al., 2022).
- **Improved nutrient uptake:** PGPR bacteria enhance the availability and uptake of nutrients, such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, by solubilizing soil minerals and fixing atmospheric nitrogen (Islam, S, M. et al., 2017).
- **Increased disease resistance:** PGPR bacteria have been found to induce systemic resistance in soybean plants, making them more resistant to various pathogens and reducing the need for chemical pesticides (Lee, B. et al., 2012).
- **Alleviation of abiotic stress:** PGPR bacteria help soybean plants tolerate and overcome abiotic stresses, such as drought, salinity, and high temperatures, by producing stress-responsive compounds and increasing the plant's antioxidant defence mechanisms. (Hao, Y. et al., 2016).

Fig. 1. PGPR Mechanisms in Soybean Crop

Challenges of PGPR Production for Soybean Crops

Although the production of PGPR for soybean crops holds significant potential, there are several challenges associated with its use. One of the challenges is the variability in the performance of different PGPR strains. Some strains may have limited effectiveness in promoting plant growth or disease resistance in soybean crops. Another challenge is the difficulty in determining the optimal inoculation dose of PGPR for soybean crops. The appropriate concentration of PGPR bacteria that will provide the maximum benefits without causing any negative effects is still unclear. Furthermore, the application methods of PGPR for soybean crops also pose challenges. Different methods such as seed coating, soil drenching, and foliar spray have been used, but the most effective and practical method is yet to be determined. (Naqqash, T. et al., 2016, Kurokura, T. et al., 2017). Additionally, the impact of PGPR on the soil microbial community and soil properties needs to be further understood. Previous studies have shown that inoculating soybeans with PGPR can significantly change the soil microbial community structure, regulate soil physical and chemical properties, and promote soybean growth (Aleksandrowicz-Trzcińska, M. et al., 2015, Qiao, Q. et al., 2017, Bai, Y. et al., 2019)

PGPR bacteria play a crucial role in enhancing root growth in soybean plants, which leads to improved nutrient uptake and overall plant development. Understanding Soybean Crop Cultivation and the impact of PGPR production is essential for optimizing soybean crop productivity. Research on the production of PGPR for soybean crops is crucial to optimize soybean crop productivity. Furthermore, it is important to consider the challenges associated with PGPR production for soybean crops.

PGPR traits used for Soybean crop

PGPR traits have been extensively studied for their potential use in enhancing the growth and productivity of

soybean crops (Kiproviski, B. et al., 2016). These beneficial bacteria, characterized as PGPR, can contribute to a range of positive effects on soybean plants. For instance, PGPR can modulate the hormonal balance in soybean plants through the production of auxins, gibberellins, abscisic acid, or 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate deaminase (Renoud, S. et al., 2022, Viso, P, D, N. et al., 2016, Naoe, L, d, M, A. et al., 2019, Miljaković, D. et al., 2022). This hormone regulation by PGPR can promote root development, nodulation, and overall plant growth in soybean crops. One key benefit is the suppression of plant pathogens through various mechanisms such as competition, antibiosis, parasitism or predation, and induction of systemic resistance. Furthermore, PGPR can play a role in maintaining optimal plant growth and development under stressful conditions that often limit crop productivity. (Viso, P, D, N. et al., 2016) (M, C. et al., 2020) (Castaldi, S. et al., 2021)

In field studies involving different crop varieties including soybean, research has shown significant improvements in germination rates, overall growth performance, and final yield when inoculated with appropriate strains of PGPR. Additionally, it has been observed that the introduction of these bacteria into the soil ecosystem effectively alters its microbial community structure while positively influencing physical and chemical properties essential for sustaining soybean growth. (Stajković-Srbinić, O. et al., 2021, Namozov, F. et al., 2022)

However successful outcomes are highly dependent on factors like selection criteria when choosing suitable types of PGPRs to be introduced into target soils alongside preferred application methods along with adequate quantities needed during the inoculation process accordingly. (Pignata, G. et al., 2016)

Moreover, several specific species among free-living bacteria belonging e.g., *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Bacillus subtilis* etc., exhibit particular affinity towards

root association. Such bacteria can establish beneficial interactions with soybean roots and provide essential growth-promoting effects. These effects include the production of siderophores, exopolysaccharides, and other metabolites that are beneficial for soybean plant growth.

Recent studies have demonstrated the successful application of PGPR for soybean growth, nutrient uptake, yield, seed quality, and soil properties. (Viso, P, D, N. et al., 2016) (Naoe, L, d, M, A. et al., 2019).

Table 01: Associated PGPRS and PGPR Mechanism (Shah, S., et al. 2018)

Mechanism	Associated PGPRS
Nitrogen fixation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Azoarcus sp.</i> • <i>Beijerinckia sp.</i> • <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> • <i>Pantoca agglomerans</i> • <i>Rhizobium sp.</i> • <i>Bacillus polymyxa</i> • <i>Azotobacter sp.</i> • <i>Rhizobia spp.</i> • <i>Azospirillum sp., etc.</i>
Production of siderophores	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Rhizobium meliloti</i> • <i>Pseudomonas sp.</i> • <i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>
Phosphate solubilization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Species of Azospirillum</i> • <i>Azotobacter</i> • <i>Bacillus</i> • <i>Beijerinckia</i> • <i>Burkholderia</i> • <i>Enterobacter</i> • <i>Erwinia</i> • <i>Flavobacterium</i> • <i>Microbacterium</i> • <i>Pseudomonas</i> • <i>Rhizobium</i> • <i>Serratia</i>
Hydrolysis of molecules released by pathogens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Pseudomonas solanacearum</i> • <i>Pseudomonas cepacia</i>
Synthesis of cyanhydric acid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>

The application of PGPR in soybean production has shown promising results in enhancing plant growth, nutrient uptake, yield, seed quality, and soil properties (Miljaković, D. et al., 2022). Several studies have shown that the introduction of PGPR in soybean crops can have significant positive effects on plant growth and overall crop productivity. The production of siderophores by PGPR is especially important as it enhances the availability of iron, an essential nutrient for soybean plants. Furthermore, PGPR inoculation has been shown to promote increased nodulation and nitrogen fixation in soybean through co-inoculation with rhizobia. (Shiro, S. et al., 2016). This is beneficial as it improves the plant's ability to acquire nitrogen, an essential nutrient for growth. In addition to these direct effects, PGPR inoculation also has indirect effects on soil microbial communities (Xing, P. et al., 2022). Previous studies have demonstrated that

the introduction of PGPR into the soil can lead to changes in the microbial community structure. These changes can improve soil physical and chemical properties, such as increasing the availability of soluble phosphorus, potassium, and other mineral elements. Furthermore, PGPR can contribute to the overall sustainability of soybean crop production by reducing the need for agrochemicals. Overall, the application of PGPR in soybean production has the potential to improve plant growth and yield, enhance nutrient uptake, optimize soil properties, and contribute to sustainable agriculture. In conclusion, the application of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria for soybean crops has shown promising results in promoting plant growth, enhancing nutrient uptake, improving seed quality, and optimizing soil properties (Sengupta, A. and Gunri, K, S., 2015, AlKahtani, D, M. et al., 2020, Namozov, F. et al., 2022).

The production of siderophores, exopolysaccharides, and other metabolites by PGPR contributes to the beneficial effects on soybean plant growth. Moreover, the co-inoculation of PGPR with rhizobia has been found to further enhance nodulation and nitrogen fixation in soybean plants (Zhao, Y. et al., 2022). The introduction of PGPR into the soil not only directly affects soybean plants but also has indirect effects on soil microbial communities, resulting in changes in soil physical and chemical properties (Xing, P. et al., 2022). These positive effects of PGPR on soybean crops make it a promising strategy for improving plant growth and overall crop productivity.

The production of siderophores by PGPR is especially important as it enhances the availability of iron, an essential nutrient for soybean plants (Li, S., Xu, B. and Gong, Y., 2016).

Siderophores produced by PGPR play a crucial role in improving the availability of iron, an essential nutrient for soybean plants. The production of siderophores by PGPR is especially important as it enhances the availability of iron, an essential nutrient for soybean plants. Siderophores are small molecules secreted by bacteria that have a high affinity for iron. Through the production of siderophores, PGPR can scavenge and solubilize iron in the soil, making it more accessible for absorption by soybean plants. (Li, S., Xu, B. and Gong, Y., 2016, Li, H. et al., 2017), Abawari, A, R., Tuji, A, F. and Yadete, M, D., 2020). This, in turn, promotes the growth and development of soybean plants as iron is a key component in various physiological processes such as photosynthesis and nitrogen fixation.

Furthermore, the production of siderophores by PGPR can also serve as a biocontrol mechanism. Since siderophores bind to iron and prevent its utilization by pathogens, they help protect soybean plants from pathogenic infections. (Li, S., Xu, B. and Gong, Y., 2016, Li, H. et al., 2017, Hanudin, H., Budiarto, K. and Marwoto, B., 2017). In addition to siderophores, PGPR also contribute to plant growth promotion through the production of phytohormones. Phytohormones are signalling molecules that regulate various aspects of plant growth and development. (Sumarsih, S. and Haryanto, D., 2012)

One example of a phytohormone produced by PGPR is indole-3-acetic acid. This phytohormone stimulates root elongation and enhances nutrient uptake in soybean plants. Another mechanism by which PGPR promotes plant growth in soybean crops is through the solubilization of inorganic phosphates. This process involves the release of organic acids by PGPR, which lower the pH of the surrounding soil and break down insoluble phosphate compounds, making them more

available for plant uptake. (Khudhur, M, A., 2017). Overall, PGPR production for soybean crops has shown significant benefits in terms of plant growth promotion and crop productivity.

Advantages of PGPR application in Soybean Crop

The application of PGPR in soybean crops offers several advantages that contribute to improved plant growth and overall crop productivity.

One of the key advantages is the ability of PGPR to enhance the availability of iron, an essential nutrient for soybean plants. Through the production of siderophores, PGPR can scavenge and solubilize iron in the soil, making it more accessible for absorption by soybean plants. This is particularly important as iron plays a crucial role in various physiological processes, including photosynthesis and nitrogen fixation. By promoting iron uptake, PGPR can significantly improve the growth and development of soybean plants. In addition, the production of siderophores by PGPR serves as a biocontrol mechanism, protecting soybean plants from pathogenic infections.

Another advantage of PGPR application in soybean crops is the production of phytohormones. Phytohormones are signaling molecules that regulate various aspects of plant growth and development. PGPR, such as indole-3-acetic acid, can stimulate root elongation and enhance nutrient uptake in soybean plants. These phytohormones promote root growth and increase the overall nutrient absorption capacity of soybean plants, leading to improved plant growth and higher crop yields

Challenges and Limitations of PGPR in soybean crop

One challenge is the variability of PGPR effectiveness. Not all PGPR strains are equally effective in promoting plant growth and crop productivity in soybean crops. This variability is influenced by factors such as the type of PGPR used, the method of inoculation, and the size of the inoculum. (Vejan, P. et al., 2016).

The effectiveness of PGPR can vary depending on the specific strain used and environmental factors, such as soil conditions and climate. Another challenge is the lack of standardized protocols for PGPR application in soybean crops. (Naqqash, T. et al., 2016) (Vejan, P. et al., 2016) There is a need for research to determine the optimal dosage and application method of PGPR in soybean crops.

This is crucial to maximize the benefits of PGPR and ensure consistent results across different farms and regions. Additionally, the cost of PGPR application may also pose a limitation for small-scale farmers. They may not have the financial resources to invest in PGPR products or the knowledge and training to properly apply them. Furthermore, the effectiveness of PGPR in soybean

crops can also be influenced by the presence of other microbial communities in the soil. These communities can compete with PGPR for resources and may hinder their establishment and effectiveness. (Naqqash, T. et al., 2016, Vejan, P. et al., 2016, Chaudhary, J, I. et al., 2020). In conclusion, the application of PGPR in soybean crops has shown potential benefits such as increased nutrient uptake, improved plant growth, and higher crop yields (Namozov, F. et al., 2022). However, several challenges and limitations need to be addressed. These include the variability of PGPR effectiveness, the lack of standardized protocols for application, the cost of PGPR products, and potential competition from other soil microbes. Despite the positive effects of PGPR on soybean crops, some certain challenges and limitations must be taken into consideration. (Naqqash, T. et al., 2016, Kurokura, T. et al., 2017). One of the main challenges in utilizing PGPR for soybean crops is the inconsistency in their performance outside of their natural habitat. This means that PGPR strains may not perform as effectively in field conditions as they do in controlled laboratory settings. This inconsistency in performance can be attributed to the variations in soil properties, climate, and other environmental factors present in different agricultural settings. (Melo, J, J. et al., 2016, Zhou, C. et al., 2017). Another challenge is the lack of standardized protocols for PGPR application in soybean crops.

There is a need for systematic research to determine the optimal dosage and application method of PGPR in soybean crops. This research should consider factors such as the specific strain of PGPR used, the growth stage of the soybean crop, and the environmental conditions prevalent in the particular agricultural setting.

Future Prospective in Soybean Crops PGPR Research

Despite the challenges and limitations associated with using PGPR in soybean crops, there is still potential for future research and advancements in this area.

One potential area for future research is the screening and selection of indigenous microbial strains that are better suited to local conditions. This can help improve the consistency and effectiveness of PGPR in soybean crops, as these indigenous strains are adapted to the specific soil and environmental conditions of the region (Viso, P, D, N. et al., 2016). Furthermore, more research can be conducted to investigate the mechanisms by which PGPR enhance nutrient uptake and plant growth in soybean crops (Naqqash, T. et al., 2016). Understanding these mechanisms can provide valuable insights into how to optimize the application of PGPR and enhance their efficacy in improving soybean crop production. Additionally, efforts can be made to develop standardized protocols for the application of PGPR in soybean crops

(Akinrinlola, J, R. et al., 2018). These protocols should consider factors such as the dosage, application method, and timing of PGPR inoculation. Moreover, future research can focus on exploring the potential synergistic effects of combining PGPR with other agricultural practices such as organic amendments or biofertilizers. By combining PGPR with these practices, it may be possible to further enhance soybean crop production and increase yields. (Naqqash, T. et al., 2016).

However, there are still challenges that need to be addressed, such as the inconsistent performance of PGPR strains under different field conditions and the lack of standardized protocols for PGPR application in soybean crops. Future research in the application of PGPR in soybean crops should focus on addressing these challenges and improving the effectiveness and consistency of PGPR performance. Furthermore, future research should also focus on understanding the long-term impacts of PGPR application on soil health and the environment. Researchers must continue to explore and advance the use of PGPR in soybean crops. (Matteoli, P, F. et al., 2018, S, G, S. and Thomas, P, J., 2019). One potential area for future research is the screening and selection of indigenous microbial strains that are better suited to local conditions. This can help improve the consistency and effectiveness of PGPR in soybean crops, as these indigenous strains are adapted to the specific soil and environmental conditions of the region. (Henagamage, A. et al., 2016)

In addition, it is important to explore the potential synergistic effects of combining PGPR with other agricultural practices, such as organic amendments or biofertilizers. By integrating these practices, farmers can potentially enhance the overall performance and benefits of PGPR in soybean crop production. Furthermore, research should also focus on studying the long-term impacts of PGPR application on soil health and the environment. Furthermore, more research is needed to investigate the specific mechanisms by which PGPR promote soybean growth and improve crop yield. (Matteoli, P, F. et al., 2018)

This can help to better understand the underlying molecular mechanisms of plant growth promotion and optimize the application methods accordingly. Furthermore, studies should also investigate the economic feasibility and practicality of implementing PGPR in soybean crop production. Overall, the use of PGPR in soybean crop production has shown promising results in improving plant growth, enhancing nutrient uptake, and increasing yields (Kurokura, T. et al., 2017). Further research and development in this field will be essential to overcome the challenges and inconsistencies associated with PGPR application. In conclusion, while the potential benefits of using PGPR in soybean crop production are

well recognized, there are still significant challenges that need to be addressed to fully harness its potential (Akinrinlola, J. R. et al., 2018). One potential area for future research is the screening and selection of indigenous microbial strains that are better suited to local conditions (Naqqash, T. et al., 2016). This can help improve the consistency and effectiveness of PGPR in soybean crops, as these indigenous strains are adapted to the specific soil and environmental conditions of the region. Additionally, it is important to explore the potential synergistic effects of combining PGPR with other agricultural practices, such as organic amendments or biofertilizers. This integrated approach has the potential to further optimize soybean crop production, improve soil health, and minimize environmental impacts. To fully understand the potential synergistic effects of combining PGPR with other agricultural practices, research should be conducted on the interactions between PGPR and organic amendments or biofertilizers in soybean crop production. (S, G, S. and Thomas, P, J., 2019, Numan, M., Serba, D, D. and Ligaba-Osena, A., 2021) Moreover, there is a need for more field-scale trials to evaluate the scalability and practicality of using PGPR in soybean crop production.

Overall, the application of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria in soybean crop production has shown promising results in improving plant growth and enhancing crop yield (Namozov, F. et al., 2022).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the use of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria in soybean crop production has proven to be a promising avenue for improving plant growth, enhancing nutrient uptake, and increasing crop yields. Studies have demonstrated that the application of PGPR can lead to significant improvements in soybean growth and productivity through the production of phytohormones, enzymes, siderophores, exopolysaccharides, and other beneficial metabolites. Additionally, co-inoculation of functional PGPR with rhizobia has been shown to enhance nodulation and nitrogen fixation. In conclusion, the use of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria in soybean crop production holds great potential for enhancing plant growth, nutrient uptake, and overall yield. Recent studies have demonstrated the successful application of PGPR in promoting soybean growth and improving the physicochemical properties of soil. The beneficial functions of PGPR, such as the production of phytohormones, enzymes, and metabolites, contribute to increased plant productivity and reduced reliance on agrochemicals.

Furthermore, the use of PGPR in combination with organic amendments or biofertilizers holds promise for further improving soybean crop production. Research on

the synergistic effects of these agricultural practices is necessary to optimize plant growth and yield while promoting soil health and minimizing environmental impacts. Field-scale trials should be conducted to assess the scalability and practicality of incorporating PGPR into soybean crop production on a larger scale.

Despite the positive effects of PGPR on plant growth and yield, there is still much to uncover regarding the underlying molecular mechanisms and interactions within soil microbial communities. More research is needed to fully understand the mechanisms by which PGPR enhances plant growth.

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